

Synthetic Studies in the Indole Field. Part IV. Some Nitroindole Derivatives of Biological Interest

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4-, 5- & 6-Nitroindole-3-aldehydes, their semicarbazones and thiosemicarbazones, the isomeric β -nitroindole-2-carboxyhydrazides and the isomeric β -nitroindole-3-acrylic acids have been prepared. The semicarbazones, thiosemicarbazones, and carboxyhydrazides are of interest as antitubercular agents and the acrylic acids as antimetabolites.

Indole-3-carboxyaldehyde thiosemicarbazone was reported by Lowell *et al.*¹ and Doyle *et al.*² to have high bacteriostatic activity *in vitro* and suppressed tuberculosis in mice. In view of this finding the present authors³ prepared 7-nitroindole-3-aldehyde, its semicarbazone, and thiosemicarbazone. We have now synthesised the isomeric 4-, 5-, and 6-nitroindole-3-aldehydes and the corresponding semicarbazones and thiosemicarbazones for evaluation of their antitubercular activity. The nitroindoles were converted into the corresponding nitroindole-3-aldehydes in high yields (90-98%) by the action of phosphorus oxychloride and dimethylformamide according to the procedure of Smith⁴. The preparation of 5- and 6-nitroindole-3-carboxyaldehydes has been reported recently by Berti and Settimo⁵ and Noland and Rieke⁶ by nitration of indole-3-carboxyaldehyde.

Brown *et al.*⁷ reported and tested indole-3-carboxyhydrazide and 6-aminoindole-3-carboxyhydrazide for antitubercular activity on account of the close similarity of their structures to those of *p*-aminosalicylic acid and isonicotinic acid hydrazide. 4-, 5- & 6-Nitroindole-2-carboxyhydrazides as well as 3-methyl-7-nitroindole-2-carboxyhydrazide have now been prepared from the corresponding ethyl nitroindole-2-carboxylates for evaluation of their bacteriostatic activity.

Indole-3-acrylic acid was shown by Fildes⁸ to inhibit the growth of both *B. coli* and *B. typhosum* and the inhibition was counteracted by the addition of tryptophan.

The nitroindole-3-acrylic acids, which would be of interest as antimetabolites, were synthesised by us from the corresponding nitroindole-3-aldehydes. The various nitroindole-3-aldehydes were condensed with diethyl malonate to obtain ethyl α -ethoxycarbonyl- β -(nitro-3-indolyl)acrylates which were further converted into the corresponding acrylic acids.

1. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, **76**, 1959.
2. *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1956, 2853.
3. *J. Karnatak Univ.*, 1961, **6**, 1.
4. *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 3842.
5. *Gazzetta*, 1961, **91**, 728; *Chem. Abst.*, 1962, **56**, 11541.
6. *J. Org. Chem.*, 1962, **27**, 2250.
7. *Ibid.*, 1956, **21**, 261.
8. *Brit. J. Exptl. Path.*, 1941, **22**, 293.

EXPERIMENTAL

Nitroindoles (4-, 5-, and 6-) were prepared from the appropriate nitrophenylhydrazones of ethyl pyruvate⁹ according to the method of Parmeter *et al.*¹⁰

6-Nitroindole from Indoline.—6-Nitroindole was also prepared from indoline according to Terent'ev *et al.*¹¹ Indoline on nitration with a mixture of HNO₃ and H₂SO₄ furnished 6-nitroindoline in 100% yield which on subsequent dehydrogenation with chloranil in xylene afforded 6-nitroindole in 80% yield.

General Method of Preparing the Aldehydes.—Phosphorus oxychloride (1 ml) was added dropwise with stirring to dimethylformamide (3.2 g.) at 10-20°. Nitroindole (1 g.) in dimethylformamide (2 g.) was then slowly added with stirring, the temperature of the mixture having been maintained at 20-30°. The mixture was kept at 45° for 1 hour and then poured on crushed ice. The clear solution was treated with an aqueous solution of NaOH (0.95 g. in water 10 ml). The mixture was boiled for a few minutes and allowed to stand when a crystalline material separated. The crystals were collected, washed with water, and dried. The nitroindole-3-aldehydes, thus obtained, were crystallised from suitable solvents. The nitroindole-3-aldehydes, their thiosemicarbazones, semicarbazones, and 2,4-DNPs are described in Table I.

TABLE I

Compounds.	*Cryst. shape.	M.P.	% Yield.	% Nitrogen Found.	% Nitrogen Reqd.
4-Nitroindole-3-aldehyde	Pale yellow, long needles (aq. EtOH)	191-92°	90%	14.62	14.73
Thiosemicarbazone	Orange prisms (MeOH)	> 320	..	26.80	26.63
Semicarbazone	Brick-red fine needles (MeOH)	Do	..	28.30	28.34
2,4-DNP	Orange crystals (EtOH)	312-15° (d)	..	22.95	22.71
5-Nitroindole-3-aldehyde	Pale yellow shining prisms (acetone)	302-303°	97.5	14.51	14.73
Thiosemicarbazone	Orange tiny needles (MeOH)	280-81° (d)	..	26.80	26.63
Semicarbazone	Yellow needles (aq. MeOH)	> 320°	..	28.61	28.34
2,4-DNP	Do	> 320°	..	22.42	22.71
6-Nitroindole-3-aldehyde	Pale yellow tiny needles (MeOH)	301-302°	97.5	14.67	14.73
Thiosemicarbazone	Orange needles (MeOH)	260-61° (d)	..	26.78	26.63
Semicarbazone	Red needles (MeOH)	255-56° (d)	..	28.58	28.34
2,4-DNP	Brick-red shining crystals (EtOH)	> 320°	..	22.90	22.71

* Solvent for crystallisation is shown in parentheses.
(d) denotes decomposition.

9. Baydon and Siddappa, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, 2462.
10. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1958, 80, 4621.
11. *Zhur. Obshch. Khim.*, 1959, 29, 2541; *Chem. Abstr.*, 1960, 54, 10991.

General Method of Preparing Nitroindole-2-carboxyhydrazides.—A mixture of appropriate ethyl nitroindole-2-carboxylate (2.5 g.), hydrazine hydrate (100%, 4 ml) and absolute ethanol (25 ml) was heated under reflux for 2 to 5 hours. On cooling, the hydrazide separating was collected, washed with ethanol, and dried. The hydrazides were purified by crystallisation from suitable solvents (Table II).

TABLE II

Carboxyhydrazides.	Crys. shape.	*M.P.	% Yield.	% Nitrogen.	
				Found.	Reqd.
4-Nitroindole-2-	Yellow shining needles (pyridine)	296-98°	76.6	25.32	25.45
5-Nitroindole-2-	Do	280-81°	70.0	25.71	25.45
6-Nitroindole-2-	Do	285-86°	65.0	25.14	25.45
3-Methyl-7-nitro- indole-2-	Do	256-57°	68.0	23.79	23.93

*With decomposition.

General Method of Preparing Nitroindole-3-acrylic Acids.—To a solution of nitroindole-3-aldehyde (2.17 g.) in pyridine (25 ml) diethyl malonate (2.4 ml) and piperidine (0.3 ml) were added. The mixture was heated under reflux for 4 hours, cooled, and poured on HCl (25 ml) containing crushed ice whereby ethyl α -ethoxycarbonyl- β -(nitro-3-indolyl)-acrylate separated as fine yellow crystals. This was filtered, washed with a little HCl (dil.) and water, and dried. These acrylates were crystallised from aqueous ethanol.

TABLE III

Name of the compound.	Cryst. shape.	M.P.	% Yield.	% Nitrogen.	
				Found.	Reqd.
Ethyl α -ethoxycarbonyl- β -(4-nitro-3-indolyl)acrylate	Yellow fine needles (aq. EtOH)	130°	90	8.63	8.44
4-Nitroindole-3-acrylic acid	Yellow powdery crystals (50% aq. EtOH)	210-12°	70	11.78	12.07
Ethyl α -ethoxycarbonyl- β -(5-nitro-3-indolyl)-acrylate	Bright yellow silky needles (aq. EtOH)	140-41°	91	8.35	8.44
5-Nitroindole-3-acrylic acid	Yellow granules (aq. EtOH)	240-41°	72	11.70	12.07
Ethyl α -ethoxycarbonyl- β -(6-nitro-3-indolyl)-acrylate	Yellow shining tiny needles (aq. EtOH)	161-62°	97	8.65	8.44
6-Nitroindole-3-acrylic acid	Yellow powdery crystals (50% aq. EtOH)	246-48°	68	11.90	12.07
Ethyl α -ethoxycarbonyl- β -(7-nitro-3-indolyl)acrylate	Yellow shining needles (aq. EtOH)	152°	95	8.58	8.44
7-Nitroindole-3-acrylic acid	Yellow crystals (50% EtOH)	264-65°	70	11.68	12.07

The preceding acrylate (2 g.) was dissolved in ethanol (50 ml) and an aqueous solution of KOH (2 g. in 10 ml) was added to it. The mixture was heated under reflux for 2 hours and poured on HCl (dil.). The yellow solid separating was collected, heated with water, dissolved in boiling 50% ethanol, and allowed to crystallise to obtain the acrylic acid.

The ethyl α -ethoxycarbonyl- β -(nitro-3-indolyl)acrylates along with their corresponding acrylic acids are described in Table III.

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